

THE ROLE OF IMAGINATION IN PSYCHOLOGICAL FORMATION OF PERSONALITY.

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Abstract: This article discusses the mental process of imagination. Imagination is the process of reorganizing impressions that reflect reality and creating new impressions based on this. Imagination is the psychological process of creating a new image, idea or idea. Illusory images differ from perceptual images and memory images in that they identify and contain what the person has not yet encountered.

Key words: Imagination, agglutination, hyperbolization, systematization, accentuation.

The formation of imaginary images can be realized only at a high level of human mental development. In many cases, imagination arises when there is a need to find a new solution, that is, in a problem situation where reflection is required beyond action. As a result of imagination, a person can foresee the future and control his behavior, creatively change the environment. Imagination is expressed by a person in a special way of mental activity formed during work.

Despite the fact that the process of imagination is a very complex reflective process, the physiological mechanisms underlying it are academic. I.P. It can be explained to some extent on the basis of Pavlov's theory of higher nervous activity. The neuro-physiological basis of imagination is the process of re-establishing and re-combining previously formed time connections (associations) in the skin of the brain.

Imagination is always directed to the practical activity of a person. Before doing something, a person imagines how it should be done and how it will be done. It creates an image of a material body that is produced in the practical activity that takes place from the beginning. Imagination is inextricably linked with human emotional experiences and the application of his will actions. Imagination is always a departure from reality, but in any situation the source of imagination is objective reality. It also performs special tasks.

- The first is to be able to express reality in images and use them to solve problems. This function of the imagination is related to thinking and is organically included in it.

- The second task is to manage emotional states. With the help of his imagination, a person will be able to satisfy many needs and reduce them as a result.

- The third function is related to the participation in human cognitive processes and states, in particular, perception, attention, memory, speech and voluntary control of emotions. With the help of images, a person has the opportunity to control perception, memories, expressions.

- The fourth task is the formation of an internal plan of action, using images and the ability to perform them in the mind.

The fifth task is to plan and program activities, to create such programs, to assess their safety and the implementation process.

Thought processes are determined by a person's experience and knowledge, as well as past experiences.

- Agglutination means "gluing", in which a new image is created by combining different parts into one.

Hyperbolization is the enlargement or reduction of images and changing individual parts.

- Systematization - smoothing the differences between some imaginations by analogy; typification is the repetition of the same images, creating images that are typical for each period.

- Accentuation - creating images by highlighting some characters. For example: friendly jokes. Accentuation is used a lot in fiction.

Summary. In conclusion, it should be noted that imagination is an important phenomenon in our life. We will try to fulfill our future dream goals, at least partially.

References:

1. G'oziyev. E. G umumiy psixologiya. Toshkent. 2002. 1-2 kitob.
2. Югай, Н. А. Мираширова "общая психология" - Ташкент 2014.
3. Дружинина В " психология ". Учебник. " Питер " 2003.
3. Najmiddinova, Rahimova Feruza, and Muxammadiev Baxromjon Baxtiyorjon o'g'li. "Factors affecting the social pedagogical activity of multimedia." INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 114-118.

4. Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "THE DESCRIPTION OF MULTIMEDIA VOCITAS AS AN INTEGRATIVE UNIT FOR IMPROVING THE SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS." American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development 15 (2023): 265-267.
5. Рахимова, Феруза. "Multimedia vositalarining ijtimoiy pedagogik faoliyatga ta'sir etuvchi omillari." Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире 1.4 (2022): 20-26.
6. Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "The Unique Power Of Improving The Social Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Vocitas." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 11.6 (2023): 604-606.
7. Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "Factors Affecting The Socio-Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Lectures." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 11.6 (2023): 601-603.

